

Synthesis of Thiaziazole Derivative from 6-Methyl-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one

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The base catalysed cyclisation of 2,6-dichloro-4-methylaryloxamide followed by halogenation with phosphorous oxychloride gave compound 2. Reaction of 2, with ammonium sulphocyanide gave compound 3, which when condensed with methyl cyanide afforded the title compound 4 with an excellent yield. This is an interesting example of hetero Diel's-Alder reaction, the 1,4-cycloaddition of isothiocyanate to acetonitrile.

SEVERAL bicyclic thiazolo-5-triazoles¹⁻⁴ have been reported to possess significant bacteriocidal, insecticidal and anthelmintic properties. Many S-triazine derivatives are commercially valuable as herbicides and fungicides^{5,6}. Similarly, bicyclic pyrrolo-S-triazoles⁷ have also been found to be useful as analeptics, CNS and respiratory system stimulants. These observations encouraged us to synthesise fused thio derivative of tricyclic triazole.

The strategy employed for the synthesis of the desired compound is shown in Scheme 1. The treatment of alkylhalo substituted aryloxamide in the presence of base catalyst gave 1,4-benzoxazin-

Scheme 1

3(2H)-one (1) followed by halogenation with phosphorous oxychloride to give pale yellow chloro compound (2) in good yields (70%). The desired halogenation in the above compounds was evident from the absence of characteristic ir absorption bands for NH (3 200-3 300 cm^{-1}) and lactam ketone (1 695 cm^{-1}).

Compound 2, in refluxing with ammonium sulphocyanide in acetone yielded thiocyanate derivative (3), which when heated with methyl cyanide afforded 4. The uv spectrum of the triazole (4), has the characteristic absorption band at λ_{max} 320 nm (C=S). This structure was also supported by the absence of ir band around 2 050 ($\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{S}$) and the presence of 1 620 (C=N) and 1 060 cm^{-1} (C=S).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded in nujol on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer and pmr on a Varian A-90 instrument using tetramethyl silane as an internal reference. All the compounds were analysed satisfactorily for C, H and N. The purity of the products, besides the elemental analysis was checked by tlc.

6-Methyl-8-bromo-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one (1): 4-Methyl-2,6-dibromophenoxyacetamide (9.0 g, 0.04 mol) and triethylamine (3.0 g, 0.03 mol) in dry methanol (40 ml) was refluxed on an oil-bath for ~6 h at 110° and the solvent was then removed under reduced pressure. The residue was extracted with ether and concentrated, the solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol to yield 2 (6.0 g, 80%), m.p. 108° (Found: C, 44.60; H, 3.33; N, 5.75. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NO}_2\text{Br}$ requires: C, 44.63; H, 3.30; N, 5.78%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 256 nm; ν_{max} (nujol) 1 695 (C=O) and 3 200 cm^{-1} (NH); δ ($\text{CD}_3-\text{COCD}_3$) 4.6 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.25 (1H, d, J 3Hz, C_7-H), 7.4 (1H, d, J 3Hz, C_8-H) and 8.8 (1H, s, br, NH).

6-Methyl-8-bromo-1,4-benzoxazin-3-yl-chloride(2): 1 (5.2 g, 0.02 mol) in phosphorous oxychloride (50 ml) and PCl_5 (1.5 g) was refluxed gently on a water-bath for ~3 h and POCl_3 was then removed under reduced pressure. The residue was triturated with ice-water (500 g). The pale

yellow solid that separated was recrystallised from ethanol (4.0 g, 80%), m.p. 130° (Found : C, 41.46 ; H, 2.68 ; N, 5.37, $C_9H_7NOClBr$ requires : C, 41.50 ; H, 2.70 ; N, 5.39%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 1 620 (C=N), 1 600 (C=C), 780 (C-Cl) ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.15 (3H, s, C_6-CH_3), 4.58 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.20 (1H, d, J 3Hz, C_7-H) and 7.35 (1H, d, J 3Hz, C_5-H).

6-Methyl-8-bromo-1,4-benzoxazin-3-yl-isothiocyanate (3) : A mixture of **2** (2.60 g, 0.01 mol) and NH_4SCN (0.76 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in acetone (30 ml) for 1 h and acetone was then removed. The residue was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol to give **3** (2.5 g, 84%), m.p. 182° (Found : C, 59.08 ; H, 3.42 ; N, 13.70. $C_{10}H_7N_2OSBr$ requires : C, 59.10 ; H, 3.45 ; N, 13.80%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 2 050 (N=C=S) and 1 600 cm^{-1} (CH=C) ; δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.15 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 4.7 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.2 (1H, d, C_7-H) and 7.35 (1H, d, C_5-H).

6-Methyl-8-bromo-4H-[1',3',5']triazolo-4'-methyl-2'-thiocarbonyl[3,4-c][1,4]benzoxazine (4) : **3** (1.4 g, 0.005 mol) was added to acetonitrile (0.21 g, 0.005 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 5 h. The solvent was then removed and the residue washed with ice-water to precipitate

the brown product which was filtered and washed with NH_4OH followed by water, and recrystallised from ethanol to furnish **4** (1.0 g, 71.5%), m.p. 220° (Found : C, 46.65 ; H, 3.22 ; N, 13.45. $C_{12}H_{10}N_4OSBr$ requires : C, 46.75 ; H, 3.24 ; N, 13.6%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 620 (C=N) and 1 610 cm^{-1} (C=S) ; δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.8 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.2 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 4.7 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.25 (1H, d, C_7-H) and 7.40 (1H, d, C_5-H).

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